

TREASoURcE

D8.1 Plan for Communication and Dissemination

WP no and title	WP8 Communication and dissemination
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This document contains the first Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP) and strategy for the TREASoURcE project (Grant Agreement No. 101059491). It comprises the description of identified targeted stakeholder groups, key messages and activities, communication materials, channels, and tools, relevant events and the related targets or KPIs. It contains also specific communication and dissemination plans for the demonstrations' communication campaigns carried out in WPs 2-5 as well as for the joint activities with the CCRI and other relevant projects. The objective is to ensure a wide outreach for the project and its results among relevant stakeholders. The CDP will be monitored and updated constantly throughout the project, and official updates will be made for each of the reporting periods.

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Acronyms and abbreviations

Acronym	Full name
BT	Business Tampere
CDP	Communication and Dissemination Plan
CE	Circular Economy
CLIC	CLIC Innovation Ltd
D	Deliverable report
ECO	ECO STOR AS
EKOF	Ekokumppanit Oy (EcoFellows)
Frstad	Fredrikstad kommune
FVH	Forum Virium Helsinki Oy
GA	Grant Agreement
GD	GreenDelta GMBH
KVC	Key value chain
KVC-DEMO	Key value chain demonstration
MTK	The Central Union of Agricultural Producers and Forest Owners
PF	Polyfuels Group AB (Previously known as Green Ideas Group GIG)
SDU	Syddansk Universitet
SE	Stakeholder engagement
SE-DEMO	Stakeholder engagement demonstration
SINTEF	SINTEF AS / SINTEF Energy
TalTech	Tallinna Tehnikaülikool
TARTU	Tartu Linn (Tartu City)
TLN	Tallinna Linn (City of Tallinn)
TOPSOE	Topsoe AS
VIKEN	Viken Fylkeskommune
VTT	VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd
WP	Work package

Executive Summary

This document contains the Plan for Communication and Dissemination designed for the TREASoURcE project. The design of TREASoURcE Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP) is part of the Task 8.1, *Dissemination and communication plan, channels and materials*, within the Communication and dissemination work package (WP8). The responsible partner for developing and implementing the CDP is CLIC. All partners will support and contribute to the communication and dissemination activities.

Well-planned and timely communication and dissemination activities are key in achieving the ambitious targets of TREASoURcE. They support the project's overall objective for an effective and widespread uptake, replication, scalability, and visibility of circular systemic solutions at local, regional, national, European and international levels. Every effort will be made to publicise the results and findings of the project via adapted channels, tools and materials. All non-confidential information and documents produced in the context of TREASoURcE will be made open access to facilitate the exchange of knowledge.

This plan covers the overall objectives of the TREASoURcE communication and dissemination activities, the main target audiences, and the key messages for each of these target stakeholder groups. It describes the selected and developed tools and channels to support the project communication and dissemination activities. Within these tools and channels, different materials, means and platforms, such as the project website and developed visual identity, social media channels, promotional materials, newsletters, press releases, scientific journals, media and participation to events are utilised. Moreover, it contains the specific plans for design and implementation of the communication campaigns related to the stakeholder engagement and key value chain demonstrations, as well as for collaboration with CCRI and other relevant projects for clustering and synergies. The last chapter includes an overview on the progress thus far as well as a preliminary workplan for upcoming months until the end of the first reporting period.

Engaging industry, relevant clusters and value chain actors as well as decision makers and local citizens and communities in the project is key for its success, since they are not only the main target audience, but also an active part of the research carried out to identify barriers and challenges for local circular economy transition. Even though the official language of the project is English, other national and regional languages may be used if considered to be the most appropriate approach to reach a wider audience at regional level.

This plan for communication and dissemination will work as a strategic tool for planning and reporting to guide and to monitor the progress of the communication and dissemination activities. It supports both consortium's internal communication and successful implementation of the workplan as well as partners' active involvement and collaboration in external communication and dissemination activities.

1. Introduction

This document describes the Plan for communication and dissemination (CDP) designed for and to be adopted by the TREASoURcE project. The design of the CDP is part of Task 8.1, Dissemination and communication plan, channels and materials, within the Communication and dissemination work package (WP8) running throughout the project period (M1-M48, 06/2022-05/2026). Its main objective is to ensure a wide outreach and visibility for the project and its results among relevant stakeholders to support a widespread uptake, replication and scalability of the systemic CE solutions identified and developed by TREASoURcE, and, on a more general level, to enhance a just transition to circular economy at local, regional, national, European, and international levels.

The specific objectives for TREASoURcE communication and dissemination (WP8) are:

- achieving visibility and making TREASoURcE an active and recognised actor in CE in the territories;
- engaging and reaching out to stakeholders via communication channels and activities;
- providing communication expertise to the other WPs in organising various stakeholder engagement workshops, campaigns, and events;
- disseminating TREASoURcE results to ensure maximum exploitation and impact.

Firstly, the CDP presents the objectives of the project communication and dissemination activities, the main target audiences, and the key messages for each of these target stakeholder groups. Secondly, it presents the selected and developed tools and channels to support the project communication and dissemination activities. Within these tools and channels, different materials, means and platforms, such as the project website and developed visual identity, social media channels, promotional materials, newsletters, press releases, scientific journals and media are utilised. In addition, it discusses the participation in conferences, workshops, and events (regional, national, transnational workshops, webinars). The key performance indicators related to each channel and tool are presented with a summary of WP8 progress from M1 (06/2022) up until M4 (09/2022) when this report is due.

In addition, the CDP contains specific communication and dissemination plans related to the stakeholder engagement (SE) and key value chain (KVC) demonstrations' campaign activities (SE- and KVC-DEMO WPs 2-5). A strategy for joint activities with the CCRI and other relevant CE projects is also presented.

The Plan for communication and dissemination will work as a strategic tool for planning and reporting to guide and to monitor the progress of the communication and dissemination activities. It will also support all consortium partners' active involvement and collaboration in communication and dissemination activities, creating and providing various communication content, contributing to the overall visibility for TREASoURcE, efficiently disseminating the findings and results at all levels (local, regional, national, European) as well as providing a framework for the communication campaigns related to the SE- and KVC-demonstrations.

The CDP will be monitored and updated regularly throughout the project, and official updates will be made for each of the reporting periods. A Final Plan for communication and dissemination will be provided at the end of the project (M48). The Communication and dissemination work package WP8 will work closely with all the other work packages. Close co-operation will be established with WP9 for collaboration

with CCRI and other projects, and with WP6 for Exploitation, replication and transferable practices to support the exploitation activities and the Exploitation Plan will partially build on the CDP.

2. Internal and external communication

The following internal and external communication activities will be undertaken during the project's lifetime and afterwards to ensure that the progress and results of TREASoURcE are efficiently and effectively communicated and disseminated to the project partners, stakeholders and broader audiences.

2.1 Internal communication

Effective internal communication within the TREASoURcE consortium is key for successful implementation of the workplan. The different work packages are highly interlinked, which underlines the need for well-structured internal communication. CLIC will engage closely with the project coordinator VTT in order to support them in any specific needs regarding to internal communication within the consortium.

VTT has created and manages a designated, password-protected Teams workspace where the consortium partners have been granted access and which contains all the project's relevant documents. This platform hosts project materials for internal use, including Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement, meeting documents (agendas, minutes, and presentations) and manuscripts in progress and project reports. This workspace serves consortium members to store and exchange files, as well to edit them online, enabling easy and collaborative document creation. All partners can upload content and edit documents online. Moreover, CLIC will test the possibility of publishing internal reminders or updates on communication and dissemination activities on a regular basis (e.g. biweekly, monthly) via Teams Chat function (or e-mail) to support all partners' engagement to communication and dissemination. If this approach proves to be successful, the reminders could also be used for joint coordination, communication, and dissemination updates when necessary.

Regular e-mail exchanges and meetings at several levels (e.g., task leader meetings, WP meetings, WP leader meetings, consortium meetings, etc.) will take place to exchange project information, update progress and share results. Consortium meetings will take place twice a year, every other being a physical meeting. Each WP has their own WP meetings together with the relevant personnel and task leaders at regular intervals.

2.2 External communication

Most of the activities described in this plan refer to the project's external communication and dissemination. The CDP serves as an internal tool for planning and reporting to guide and to monitor the progress of the communication and dissemination activities. On the other hand, it sets the means and targets for all the communication and dissemination activities implemented throughout the project lifetime.

Every effort will be made to publicise the results and findings of the project via adapted channels, tools and materials. All non-confidential information and documents produced in the context of TREASoURcE will be made open access to facilitate the exchange of knowledge.

All partners are expected to support communication and dissemination to ensure that a broad range of relevant stakeholders will be reached and engaged throughout the lifetime of the project. This is especially important since each partner in TREASoURcE has their own (sectoral, local, regional, national, value chain, etc.) network of stakeholders. Partners' activities may include but are not limited to: sharing content about the project on social media and on each entity's respective website or newsletter, engaging with relevant national and local media (print, radio, television, web-based) and with stakeholders. Whenever possible, partners will translate the press releases into their national languages and share them with the local media. Partners may also hold face-to-face meetings with interested parties and attend conferences, trade fairs and other events to disseminate the project. A shared file for tracking all the communication and dissemination activities has been provided to the consortium. It can be accessed and updated in the project Teams workspace. The partners are encouraged to log in their communication and dissemination activities with relevant details (e.g., channel, place, time, responsible partner, number of stakeholders reached, link to the content if possible) as soon as these take place in order to facilitate their reporting towards EC. Reminders will be sent regularly by CLIC to ensure that all relevant activities (past or upcoming) are gathered in the file. In addition, all partners must proactively share information with CLIC about their activities related to the project, such as attendance to conferences, as well as the project's developments and results, so that CLIC can share the information on the project website and social media channels in a timely manner. CLIC will also support all partners in the communication needs (planned or *ad hoc*) of other work packages.

2.3 Levels of external communication and dissemination

The TREASoURcE key target groups operate at different geographic levels, which has an influence on the communication tools, channels and media to be employed.

2.3.1 European level – European Commission (EC) and Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI), Standardization bodies

The EC, the CCRI and the CCRI-CSO will be informed about the results via the periodic reporting of the project (midterm review, minutes of periodical meetings, updates of this document), to announce relevant milestones, and to propose collaboration with other ongoing projects on dissemination activities. Furthermore, close collaboration will be established with the CCRI and the CCRI-CSO, with participation to the organized workshops and other events, such as webinars and focus groups, as well as other bilateral exchanges.

2.3.2 International level – Industry, Scientific Community

The relevant international organisations will be informed of the project results. Scientific knowledge can be translated into practical information, guidelines, and regulatory policies. Direct mailing to specific organisations and stakeholders will be used to distribute electronic resources to raise public awareness. Technical journals, conferences and workshops at both national and international level, industry meetings, and participation in industrial forums will also be used for the dissemination of knowledge both at research and industrial levels.

2.3.3 National and regional level – Industry, Decision makers, Citizens and communities, Standardization bodies

Engaging industry, relevant clusters and value chain actors as well as decision makers and local citizens and communities in the project is key for its success, since they are not only the main target audience, but also an active part of the research carried out to identify barriers and challenges for local circular

economy transition. WP2 activities for stakeholder engagement will play a central role to contact and involve the relevant stakeholders from targeted countries and regions. CLIC will support them in elaborating key messages and materials as well as carrying out targeted communication campaigns when needed.

Even though the official language of the project is English, other national and regional languages may be used if considered to be the most appropriate approach to reach a wider audience at regional level. If any materials need to be translated, the regional partners will be responsible for translating, while CLIC will ensure that an overall uniform look and feel can be maintained with designs that follow the overall project identity and guidelines.

2.4 Communication phases

The project communication activities can be grouped under three main phases according to the main focus of the activities and content.

In the first phase, as the project activities are gradually starting and results are being generated, the project communication activities will focus on building awareness about the project, its objectives and expected impact, as well as overall awareness about the circular economy and its benefits:

- TREASoURcE objectives and methodology, upcoming activities
- background, information on the three key value chains and why it is important to develop circular systemic solutions in these value chains
- TREASoURcE partners, people and organisations involved in the project
- expected impact of TREASoURcE
- role and possibilities of citizens and communities in CE and the systemic CE solutions
- impact of everyday life practices on sustainability and circular economy transition
- success stories, real-life experiences and concrete examples to make the message more understandable and relatable

The list of planned topics and content is not exhaustive but gives an overall idea of the planned emphasis for the first phase. Many of the topics mentioned above are also highly relevant going forward in the project since they are part of building the core message of TREASoURcE.

In the second phase, the communication content is extended from the core messages presented above to the ongoing activities and, notably, to the demonstrations, campaigns, and any possible preliminary results. The plan for campaign activities to support the realization of the SE- and KVC-demos is described in more detail in chapter 6. Communication activities will include, in general, announcing events and providing summaries and digital content after the events have taken place. Moreover, public deliverables will be made available for dissemination via the TREASoURcE communication channels once they have been reviewed and approved. Executive summaries containing the main information from each deliverable will also be published to support the dissemination and to help interested stakeholders find information that is relevant to them. In collaboration with the project partners, CLIC will extract key messages and highlight interesting findings in short, easy-to-read formats that will be posted on the TREASoURcE website and social media. The communication of the project activities and outcomes will be further supported by social media campaigns to generate traffic to the website.

In the third phase, the timeline of the dissemination and communication activities will be strongly correlated to the deliverables timeline and the outputs and other materials produced. Announcements on social media will be synchronised with updates on the project progress and activities on the project website as they occur, intending to redirect the users to the website acting as the main dissemination and communication platform. Moreover, replication and transfer of good practices will be supported by targeted actions to support especially WP6 activities. Wide dissemination of project outputs, e.g. the Replication Handbook and policy recommendations, will be ensured by targeted measures that will be described in more detail in the updated version of the CDP (by M18 and M36).

3. Target audiences and key messages

The key messages have been defined with the purpose of reaching different audiences effectively, including industry, citizens, consumers and communities, scientific community, cities, municipalities and regions, relevant networks or ecosystems, and decision makers with the objective to benefit the project results. The website will be provided with information matching the particular interests and needs of each target group and subgroup.

TREASoURcE communication and dissemination and the key messages have been organised around three main themes: 1) Project, its benefits (societal, economic, environmental, political) and results; 2) CE awareness raising; 3) Key value chains and DEMOs. The emphasis between the different themes and inside them vary according to the different phases presented in chapter 2. Similarly, it varies depending on the targeted stakeholder groups. Key messages will be developed during the project with more detail and with more finetuned and targeted messages. More finetuned versions will be included in the next official update of the CDP (M18), adapted according to the input and insights from the SE- and KVC-DEMOs. Target groups, objectives and key messages are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Target groups, objectives and key messages

Target group	Objectives and key messages
Market / Industrial stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Generate interest among early adopters - Wide outreach and cooperation with value chain actors in the three key value chains - Promote uptake of individual project results - Get feedback from target audience, provide solutions to perceived risks - Share success stories, foster sustainability in the sector - Increase awareness of the capabilities and uses of the TREASoURcE Replication Handbook - Support successful replication of the identified CE solutions
Citizens, Consumers and Communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness raising campaigns with various activities engaging citizens among other stakeholders - Educate and deepen understanding of the role and possibilities of citizens and communities on systemic CE solutions

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inspire for changing everyday life practices, communicating everyday issues about CE to build awareness in the general public - Circularity as a way of living is sustainable, possible and pleasant - Fostering acceptance of recycled products/products with recycled content - Illustrative and didactic graphic and video materials - Practical examples on how TREASoURcE is promoting circular economy and sustainability goals, and about its societal, economic and environmental benefits
Scientific community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inform about the scientific project results - Education and training of new experts in CE - Sharing results, knowledge diffusion with other experts, opening further research paths - Getting feedback and new contacts with academic and nonacademic experts and groups working in CE
Municipalities, Cities and Regions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness raising about CE and circular systemic solutions - Fostering replication and exploitation of results - Educate and deepen understanding of the role and possibilities of municipalities, cities and regions in and the potential of the CE - Strong linkage to the CCRI and Pilots
Standardization bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technical characteristics/specifications - Compliance of pyrolysis and 2nd life battery products and processes with current standards, and/or feeding the development of new and adapted standards
Policy and decision makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Suggest improvements to overcome local, national and EU-level regulatory barriers preventing CE transition and scalability - Foster the replication and the public-private link - Increase awareness of the capabilities and uses of the TREASoURcE Replication Handbook
Networks, Clusters and Ecosystems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Informing about the project and its results
Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness campaigns aiming for a wide coverage in TREASoURcE countries and regions - Potential of the circular economy in Europe for creating well-being (societal, environmental), wealth and jobs - Usefulness of EU R&D and initiatives like CCRI - Illustrative and didactic graphic and video materials
Other CCRI and CE projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ensure synergies and enable wide exploitation to enhance the use of new knowledge in CE beyond the project - Prevent duplication of undertaken research actions or any generated information or findings

TREASoURcE has ambitious targets with regard to engaging in an active two-way exchange with various stakeholder groups via activities related to stakeholder engagement and key value chain demonstrations (WPs 2-5).

4. Tools and channels

Different tools and channels will be used to disseminate and communicate the activities carried out by TREASoURcE, as well as its results. Each tool and channel will be used appropriately to address different target groups at different stages of the project implementation, thereby increasing the efficiency of the dissemination plan. The connections between the tools and channels, the target groups and the expected impacts are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Communication channels and tools

Channel	Tool	Target groups	Expected impact
Online presence	<i>Website</i>	All stakeholders	Raise awareness about the project, its goals, expected impacts and inform about its benefits. Raise awareness about CE, deepen understanding of the role and possibilities of citizens and communities on systemic CE solutions. Inform on the day-to-day activities and achievements of the project, upcoming events, and the achieved milestones.
	<i>Newsletter</i>	Industry, academia, public bodies, decision makers	
	<i>Social media</i>	Media, general public, value chain actors, industry, academia, public bodies	
	<i>Blog posts</i>	Industry, academia, public and funding bodies, decision makers, media, citizens	
	<i>Videos</i>	All stakeholders	
	<i>Podcast series</i>	Industry, academia, public and funding bodies, decision makers, media, citizens	
Printed materials	<i>Promotional materials: presentations, leaflets, roll-up, brochures, etc.</i>	Consortium, all stakeholders	Raise awareness about the project, its goals, expected impacts and inform about its benefits.
Publications	<i>Press releases</i>	Media, all stakeholders and general public	Inform about the (scientific) project results, open further research paths, education, training of new experts in CE. Sharing results, knowledge diffusion with other experts, getting feedback and new contacts with academic and non-academic experts and groups working in CE.
	<i>Scientific publications, articles</i>	Academia, Industry	
Events	<i>Presentations, posters in events</i>	Industry, Academia	Generate interest among early adopters; cooperation; promote uptake of

	(sectoral, scientific)		individual project results; foster sustainability in the sector, get feedback from target audience, replication of the successful CE solutions.
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External communication and dissemination activities build on the preliminary plan presented in Section 2.2 of the Grant Agreement. The tools and channels include the visual identity and different templates, the project website, articles targeted to both lay and technical audiences, press releases, e-newsletters, blog posts, podcasts, scientific papers and leaflets, social media presence, and participation in various events: workshops, conferences, expositions and such. The journal articles are primarily intended to communicate the results to the scientific and academic communities. Project presentations at sectoral and scientific conferences are intended to reach industry and market stakeholders and academia.

4.1 Visual identity

A project identity has been developed to build a uniform and recognizable visual brand for TREASoURcE. The project identity offers a package of templates that will facilitate the building of reputation progressively throughout the project. It will also support the coordination of content creation between different consortium partners and helps to attain a uniform look and feel. This includes a project logo and color palette, graphic elements and typography, which are presented in the accompanying brand guidelines. These are being consistently used for the project website and all other communication materials and templates, such as PowerPoint presentations, Word documents, flyers, brochures and posters. Figure 1 below presents the project logo and the designed signature visual appearance.

Figure 1. Project logo and signature visual appearance

Any dissemination activities and publications in the project, including the project website, will specify that the project has received funding from the European Union. The EU emblem will be displayed with the funding statement. These instructions are also specified in the brand guidelines in Annex 1.

4.2 Project website

Operational as of Month 3, the project website <https://treasource.eu/> has been created to serve as a central information point for the various stakeholders and media; it has been designed to be the main information repository for the project, its objectives, results and findings, and all activities related to its developments and progress. All communication materials and any other non-confidential documentation related to TREASoURcE will be either published on or linked to the project website.

The content and messages incorporated have been defined with the purpose of reaching different audiences, including industry, citizens and communities, scientific community, and policy makers with the objective to benefit the project results. The website will be provided with information matching the particular interests and needs of each target group and subgroup. It has been designed to support intuitive navigation to help visitors find content that is pertinent to them. The website has a key role in communication and dissemination of the results and findings as well as in creating the overall impact of the project. To generate the needed statistical data and to monitor the performance, the TREASoURcE website is using Matomo Analytics.

The TREASoURcE website has been designed for a user-friendly experience with a layout that enhances the visibility of the project brand. The modern layout follows the overall look and feel set by the developed project visual identity: logo, color palette, typography, graphic elements, and images. Figure 2 presents a screenshot from the website homepage to get an idea of the overall look and feel of the site.

Figure 2. Project website homepage

The site is not a static tool. It will be managed by CLIC, further developed, and updated regularly throughout the project lifetime. All partners will contribute to the content creation, share their progress and other activities. The website will remain accessible for two years after the project's completion.

A full description of the design and launch of the project website is presented in D8.4.

4.3 Social media

A social media presence has been established for TREASoURcE (by M1) on:

- Twitter: https://twitter.com/TREASoURcE_eu/ @TREASoURcE_eu
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/treasure/> / @TREASoURcE

Social media are crucial for the dissemination and communication of the project, since the outreach and engagement of stakeholders is of utmost importance in order to attain the overall objectives of TREASoURcE. In addition, having a broad range of networks ensures a wide dissemination to different age groups and target audiences. Content will be posted on social media regularly from the very start of the project to increase outreach. Social media channels are used as a tool to announce project achievements, upcoming events, workshops, and such. Most importantly, it is utilised to drive traffic to the project website with the use of different calls to action included in the posts (e.g. More information on our website, Visit our website to learn more, More information and registration on our website, etc.).

Currently, Twitter and LinkedIn accounts have been set up. The possibilities and the benefits of creating further profiles on Facebook and Instagram will be explored related to the upcoming demo campaigns. The idea is that further social media channels could be benefitted to gain even broader outreach to different target and age groups for the dedicated campaigns. However, the creation of further profiles will be done in a strategic and timely manner in order to assure that relevant and adapted content can be provided to each channel.

The social media accounts will be managed by CLIC with support from the partners. Consortium partners are encouraged to follow the project social media channels and engage with them as much as possible. Whenever possible, the partners will share posts on their own corporate websites and social media networks, to further extend the outreach.

WP8 has prepared and provided (by M1) the consortium with a specific guide for using the different social media channels for project purposes and for maximizing the impact of the social network. It includes the links, handles and hashtags for TREASoURcE social media profiles, recommended other handles or hashtags to use in posts (notably Horizon Europe and CCRI-related handles), as well as tips or good practices to take into consideration when posting via partners' accounts. The guide is meant as a living document to be updated and completed with relevant information throughout the project, whenever necessary. The social media guide can be found in its entirety in Annex 2.

4.4 Promotional materials and publications

A general presentation, a brochure, a poster, a factsheet, and a roll-up will be developed by M12 for distribution to partner networks and at conferences, exhibitions, workshops, and training sessions. The first versions of these materials will contain general information of the project activities, objectives, participants and the expected results. Updated versions will be created further on in the project to support the dissemination of results once these will be available. A general PowerPoint presentation is under preparation, which will include key information on the project's objectives, methodology, partners, expected impact, results and so forth. These materials may be complemented with others elaborated later in the project and updated if needed. All promotional materials are open access and will be made available on the project website under the 'Publications' section: <https://treasure.eu/publications/>.

4.5 E-Newsletter

An electronic newsletter will be prepared and published twice per year. The newsletter will include project updates, announcements, interviews and other timely information related to TREASoURcE, to be distributed to stakeholders and partner networks and posted on the project website. Moreover, project updates may appear in partners' respective newsletters, which are distributed electronically to their own contacts within their specific industry. CLIC will coordinate the newsletter compilation with all partners creating and providing content.

A subscription form is permanently available on the project website. Moreover, CLIC will share the subscription information on project's social media channels inviting the audience to subscribe. For further support in building a list of subscribers, CLIC will prepare an email template introducing briefly the project and inviting to subscribe to the newsletter. This email will be shared by each partner with the stakeholders they know in a personalised email, so that GDPR is being respected and no personal data is handled without prior permission.

A total of at least eight (8) newsletters will be issued during the project period. Additional newsletters may be published as part of joint activities with the CCRI and other relevant CE projects or projects funded under the same topic (namely, the SYSCHEMIQ project).

4.6 Press releases

Press releases will be prepared and published to announce any newsworthy developments during the course of the project. CLIC will prepare official English version for the European press and the partners are encouraged to translate and share them with national and regional media. Local media from the partners' countries will be leveraged, as they are more likely to publish the news than big national media. The overall aim is to gain visibility and coverage for the project and the more general topic of circular economy in the national media.

4.7 Scientific papers

Knowledge advancements developed within TREASoURcE will form the basis for scientific publications, to be disseminated to the scientific community, actors in the three key value chains, other stakeholders, as well as policymakers. To support informing about the scientific project results and opening further research paths as well as diffusing knowledge and enhancing the training of new experts in circular economy, a target of 5 to 10 peer-reviewed papers is aimed at for publications in selected, targeted journals, such as:

- Materials Circular Economy,
- International Journal of Circular Economy and Waste Management,
- Polymer-Plastics Technology and Materials,
- Energy and Environmental Science,
- Journal of Energy Storage,
- Journal of Cleaner Production,
- International Journal of Civic Engagement and Social Change.

The articles will be open access to other researchers either by self-archiving online or via open access publishing on the journal website.

4.5 Participation to events

As part of the dissemination activities, project partners will attend to relevant sectoral (incl. scientific) events, conferences, fairs, workshops and webinars both online and offline to meet with target groups, other stakeholders and public authorities and to raise awareness about the project, its objectives, progress and results. These events provide access to target audiences at local, regional, national, European and international levels and they are a great channel to generate interest and promote uptake of individual project results among industrial stakeholders and early adopters.

Conference participation may include presentations, posters or distribution of flyers in addition to directly engaging with stakeholders. A target of 10 to 15 presentations held or posters displayed at targeted conferences has been set to ensure a wide outreach. The targeted conferences and events include local and international key value chain seminars, such as:

- Circular Materials Conference,
- Pollutec,
- Green Week,
- International Conference on Sustainable Waste Management,
- Waste Management and Resource Optimisation,
- International Conference on Plastic Recycling and Waste Management,

- All4Climate (JRC),
- Plastics Recycling Show Europe,
- K Trade Fair,
- FarmEurope and EIP-AGRI events,
- Circular Energy Storage,
- Nordic Battery events.

Since TREASoURcE encompasses three different key value chains, diverse forums will be utilised to disseminate the project and its results. In addition, the consortium will search for further opportunities for synergies in events organised by other relevant EU-funded projects (e.g. the SYSCHEMIC project), events organised by other CCRI related projects (e.g. EcoeFISHent, Agro2Circular, CIRCULAR FOAM) or by relevant networks or platforms (e.g. European SusChem Technology Platform, Plastics Alliance, Battery2030+, Nordic Circular Hotspot). The overall target at pan-European level is to reach at least 100 000 entrepreneurs to disseminate about the demonstrated, new circular business models (e-marketplace, KVC-demos). The list of events will be reviewed and updated regularly (e.g. in every other WP8 meeting) in collaboration with partners to ensure the project's presence in relevant dissemination events.

In addition, the project will organise a broad range of events, workshops, webinars etc. to disseminate about the project and to enhance the CE transition and the uptake of the circular systemic solutions. Lots of these activities are planned and take place as part of the SE- and KVC-DEMOS and the related demo campaigns. The specific plan for the communication campaigns is presented in chapter 6. At the end of the project period, a final conference (online/offline) will be organised for wide outreach and efficient dissemination of the results to maximise the impact of TREASoURcE and to set the framework for exploitation activities beyond the project lifetime.

5. Measuring impact

The successful implementation of the Communication and Dissemination Plan will be measured by the achievement of specific targets that are monitored throughout the project. The activities and actions undertaken by the project will be updated and adjusted based on the progress of these indicators. Table 4 presents an overview of the set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for TREASoURcE communication and dissemination activities.

Table 3. Means, target audiences and KPIs

Means	Target audience	KPI
Website	All stakeholders	N ^o visits: 5 000
Newsletter	Industry, academia, public bodies, decision makers	N ^o of publications: 8 N ^o of subscribers: 500 N ^o of views: 2 000
Press releases	Media, all stakeholders and general public	N ^o of publications: 4-8 N ^o of contacted media: 500

Promotional materials: presentations, leaflets, brochures, etc.	Consortium, all stakeholders	N° of publications: 5-8 online versions N° of downloads: 500
Social media	Media, general public, value chain actors, industry, academia, public bodies	N° of followers: 200 (per channel) N° of posts: 80 (per channel)
Videos	All stakeholders	N° of videos: 2-4 N° of views: 300
Blog posts	Industry, academia, public and funding bodies, decision makers, media, citizens	N° of publications: 8-15 N° of views: 800
Podcast series	Industry, academia, public and funding bodies, decision makers, media, citizens	N° of publications: 4-8 N° of listening sessions: 250
Scientific publications	Academia, Industry	N° of papers: 5-10 peer-reviewed papers
Presentations at conferences, seminars, fairs, workshops and other events	Industry, Early adopters, Academia	N° of presentations: 10-15 presentations at targeted events
PhD, MSc and BSc thesis in project context	Academia	N° of thesis: 2-4
Policy recommendations	Decision makers	N° of policy recommendations: 5-15 local/national/EU-level policy recommendations (in cooperation with relevant projects and CCRI)
Joint activities with CCRI	All relevant stakeholders	N° of joint activities: 4-10
Regional, national or transnational workshops, webinars: training, SE-DEMOS campaigns	Value chain actors, industry, academia, public bodies, decision makers, regional actors, NGOs, investors, citizens, schools	N° of workshops/webinars: 20-30

The joint activities with CCRI and relevant projects as well as the plan for the demo campaign activities are described in more detail in chapters 6 and 7.

6. Plan for communication campaigns

The expected results of TREASoURcE will have a consistent and maximised impact only if they will be communicated and disseminated well, using the best tools and reaching the relevant stakeholders and decision makers that can boost the transition to CE and the uptake of systemic CE solutions. For this purpose, TREASoURcE adopts a cooperative approach, establishing and maintaining active exchanges with stakeholders covering all the target key value chains via targeted and tailored communication and dissemination efforts. One of the key activities of TREASoURcE to boost the CE transition and the uptake of circular systemic solutions is the realisation of the SE- and KVC-DEMOS: stakeholder engagement

and key value chain demonstrations. To support the successful implementation and boost the overall visibility of the demos, the CDP includes a specific plan for the communication campaign activities.

The campaign activities are different from general communication and dissemination efforts in the sense that they may be implemented on a local or national level which always requires adapting the content to the given cultural, societal and linguistic context. The objective of this plan is to support the coordination and implementation of the campaign activities (e.g., clarifying responsibilities) as well as to provide a framework and guidelines for the upcoming activities. CLIC is the overall responsible for coordinating the activities and providing templates and tools to be adapted in local conditions. Like the SE- and KVC-DEMOS, also the campaign activities are built such that they are interlinked, supporting and complementing each other, thus building a coherent narrative and contributing to the overall impact of TREASoURcE. The overall objectives include:

- Coherent, adapted and understandable messages for the identified target audiences
- Influencing citizens, communities, value chain actors and decision makers to understand their role and the benefits of CE and to, eventually, embrace and become actors in the CE transition
- Actionable communication material for the use of TREASoURcE partners

This document includes a first version of the plan, which will be updated once more information on the demonstrations, the circular economy framework and the potential barriers for CE transition in each region will be available. Specific meetings between CLIC and all the relevant partners (e.g. the regional partners and demo leaders) will be organised in order to coordinate the creation and design of the needed materials and templates for the campaigns. The final campaign actions, once implemented, may cover a broad variety of different activities such as: events (e.g. workshops, webinars, conferences, exhibitions), publications (e.g. distribution of materials such as flyers, videos, podcasts, posters), social media campaigns (including targeted use of sponsored ads) and site visits organised for relevant value chain actors.

6.1 Methodology

The following steps will be taken in order to understand the incentives of each target group and to build credible narratives based on them:

1) Defining the target audiences

The target groups for the campaigns will be defined and described in detail. It is important to take into consideration the different geographical and cultural areas inside TREASoURcE territories while defining the target groups. As part of the CDP, an overall definition of target groups has been done. However, for the campaign purposes, these need to be divided in more defined subgroups or segments in order to determine, for example, the most effective channels for reaching each of the target groups. Close collaboration with WPs 1 and 2 will be crucial in order to better understand the current state-of-the-art of CE in the regions as well as the motivations of each given target group.

2) Developing key messages

Key messages and arguments will be drafted based on each target audience's specific incentives and motivations. The benefits from each group's perspective will be identified, and real-life stories and concrete examples will be identified, gathered and utilised to make the message credible, understandable and relatable.

3) Defining the channels

Once the target audiences have been defined, their media use needs to be further examined. This will help to determine the appropriate channels for reaching each target audience respectively. National, regional and local levels need to be taken into consideration. A broad range of channels, tools and materials will be utilised.

4) **Developing narratives**

A first set of narratives will be developed, taking into consideration the respective target audiences and the used channels. Different storyline types may be applied.

5) **Testing the narratives**

The testing will take place through a set of workshops with relevant stakeholders. The narratives will be adjusted based on feedback from the workshops.

6) **Providing templates and framework for the campaign activities**

CLIC will provide templates and/or materials and an overall framework for the implementation of the campaign activities to the partners. Each partner has reserved resources to adapt the materials to local conditions.

7) **Implementing the campaign activities**

Clarifying each partner's role and responsibilities is crucial for successful implementation of the plan. The ownerships need to be considered from both substance and geographical aspects (depending on the scale of each campaign: local, national, European, etc.).

6.2 Campaign themes

The consortium partners have brainstormed ideas on potential campaign themes in a dedicated workshop that took place during the face-to-face kick-off in Helsinki on 17.8.2022. Since the final content of the campaigns will come directly from the demos and benefit the synergies created by the interlinkages between the different demos, it would be counterproductive to define specific or final themes at this stage. The potential themes identified include:

- Waste prevention (or reduction)
- Educating and raising awareness on plastic recycling among citizens and consumers
- Promoting plastics sorting and collection
- Plastics and other waste ending up in the environment if not appropriately disposed of
- Enhancing understanding on citizens' role as CE actors, making complex issues understandable and relatable
- Urban-rural symbiosis
- Dedicated campaigns for children (e.g. in schools, science centres)
- Increasing awareness on CE principles, new business opportunities and requirements from a procurement perspective (based on best practices so far, EU regulation and legislation), targeting service providers and city officials
- Enhancing the collection of bio-based materials by highlighting the short and long-term benefits to the relevant stakeholders (e.g. farmers, forestry, municipalities etc.)
- Raising awareness on the reuse possibilities of bio-based side and waste streams
- Avoiding food waste
- Using or favouring local resources
- Battery demo sites: informing about the selected sites, motivations and expected outcomes of the project
- Battery installations generating savings in electricity use

6.3 Identified challenges for implementation

The identified challenges relating to the campaign implementation and attaining the set targets include:

- Varying motivations, interests and attitudes of target audiences
- Varying levels of knowledge and CE awareness across the TREASoURcE regions
- Making technical and/or complex topics simple, comprehensible and interesting
- Difficulties in changing attitudes and behaviours in a society

These challenges are partly addressed inherently by the way the project and the consortium have been structured. An important amount of regional and public actors is present in the project consortium. They are naturally present locally in the TREASoURcE regions and are aware of the local conditions. On the other hand, a broad range of participative actions is taking place in WP2 in order to map e.g. stakeholders attitudes and levels of knowledge or awareness about CE. The project will engage in a two-way exchange locally with the relevant stakeholders to better understand their incentives and roles. As part of the plan for communication campaigns, frameworks for target group specific narratives will be established, taking into consideration each key value chain as well as each TREASoURcE region. These will take into consideration the specific conditions in each of the TREASoURcE regions, and utilise the input from WP1, WP2 as well as from each of the key value chains and from the regional partners. The narratives will be tested and further developed.

6.4 Timeline for implementing the plan

Below is presented a preliminary timeline with the first steps for implementing the plan for communication campaign activities. Since the timeline is dependent on the implementation and findings of the demonstrations (Stakeholder Engagement and Key Value Chain Demos, WPs 3-5) and as well as WP1 and WP2, further steps will be identified and defined in the next version of the CDP (M18).

- 1) A common structure and guidelines for the campaign work will be prepared and presented to partners during the consortium meeting in M7
- 2) Opportunities and potential topics or titles for campaigns will be identified by M12
- 3) During the next face-to-face consortium meeting (M12/13), a dedicated session will be organised to further develop the campaign ideas together.

7. Plan for joint activities with CCRI and relevant projects to create synergies

In order to ensure synergies, avoid any duplication of generated information and to facilitate wide exploitation of the project results and findings to enhance the use of new knowledge in CE beyond the project and its immediate stakeholders, TREASoURcE seeks opportunities for collaboration with relevant other initiatives. Close, continuous co-operation with CCRI, sister projects and other relevant initiatives (especially LC-GD-3-2-2020 projects) is actively sought for by the consortium. This document contains the first version of the plan for joint activities with CCRI and other relevant projects for clustering and creating and boosting synergies. It will be monitored and updated regularly throughout the project, and official updates will be made for each of the reporting periods.

7.1 Identifying clustering opportunities

A strong connection and contact to CCRI and CCRI-CSO is ensured by the very design of the project. CCRI collaboration and CCRI-CSO clustering activities are embedded in the work plan on task level under both WP8 (Communication and dissemination) and WP9 (Coordination and management). Close collaboration has already been established between T9.5 (led by VTT) and T8.2 CCRI collaboration subtask (led by CLIC) with regular e-mail exchanges between the task leaders and with CCRI and CCRI-CSO representatives. A direct link has also been established through a joint meeting (virtual Teams meeting) with the CCRI and CCRI-CSO representatives.

In regards to clustering with sister projects and other relevant projects, a comprehensive list of relevant projects (past and on-going) has been included in the Grant Agreement. This list will be benefited to 1) build on existing knowledge and to avoid any repetition and overlaps, 2) contact relevant ongoing projects for clustering and joint activities. The consortium is in the process of compiling an extensive list of relevant projects to identify and coordinate the opportunities for clustering and synergies. These can be benefited e.g. for exchange of best practices, knowledge on CE, generated results and data or extending existing networks.

7.2 Joint activities

A wide range of potential joint activities has been identified by the consortium. These include:

- joint workshops, webinars or other joint events
- information exchange of activities and research (best practices, methodologies, results in general, data, networks, knowledge on CE, etc.)
- joint newsletters, videos, podcast
- joint policy feedback (coordinated with the SYSCHEMIQ project)
- TREASoURcE participation in regular CCRI-CSO workshops (2xyear), biennial CCRI general conference (every 2 years)
- Communication of CCRI-CSO activities and events in TREASoURcE channels
- Communication of TREASoURcE activities and events as well as results in CCRI-CSO channels
- TREASoURcE stakeholder engagement and replication activities, results and lessons learned: input to the CCRI Pilots
- TREASoURcE participation and/or input to CCRI Pilots working groups
- Final conference in co-operation with CCRI and relevant projects

In addition to the preliminary listing of ideas presented above, it has already been confirmed that a CCRI-CSO member will be included in TREASoURcE Advisory Board. This will ensure a strong and continuous link between the project and the CCRI-CSO and help to identify and align needs on both sides. What is more, TREASoURcE will lead a joint education video targeted to citizens and communities, '*Ways for citizens to make a sustainable difference in their everyday lives*', which will describe how to incorporate circular practices into everyday lives, with other CCRI projects and with CCRI-CSO. In order to facilitate the coordination of this activity and further ones, TREASoURcE will also propose to initiate Communication Managers Joint Project Committee across CCRI projects to stay on-top of project developments and increase collaboration (biannual).

8. Progress and upcoming activities

8.1 Actions carried out in M1-M4

The communication and dissemination work package is active throughout the whole project duration. Lots of activities, in particular relating to project brand building, have already taken place since M1 of TREASoURcE, i.e. June 2022.

8.1.1 Project identity and materials

At the very start of the project (by M1), a visual identity for TREASoURcE was created with accompanying brand guidelines (Annex X). It includes the logo of the project, the brand guidelines (color palette, typography, graphic elements, guidance on the use of the project logo and the EU emblem with the funding statement, and image style) and a set of templates (PowerPoint template, Word template for reports and a 1-pager). All these materials have been shared with the partners and updated as the project progresses if judged necessary. The developed PowerPoint template is included in Annex 3.

8.1.2 Press release

A press release was published on June 22nd, 2022 to announce the start of the project. An English version was prepared and sent by CLIC to 272 relevant journalists and media. The e-mailing was done via Melwater platform concentrating on the geographical area covered by the project (namely Finland, Sweden, Norway, Denmark and Germany). Since all TREASoURcE regions were not covered by the used platform, a request was made to especially Baltic consortium members to circulate the press release in their respective networks. All partners were encouraged to translate the press release in their native language to gain even more wider coverage and visibility in the regions.

The press release was also published on CLIC website, and the link was distributed via TREASoURcE and partner social media accounts (e.g. ECO STOR LinkedIn account (<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6950044675068051456/>), Viken/Klima Østfold Facebook account (<https://www.facebook.com/klimaostfold/>)).

Related newspaper articles were published in three local newspapers in Norway: *Demokraten*, *Fredrikstad blad* (<https://www.f-b.no/far-14-millioner-for-a-undersoke-sirkularokonomi/s/5-59-2648336>), and *Dagsavisen* (<https://www.dagsavisen.no/demokraten/nyheter/2022/06/29/fredrikstad-med-i-internasjonalt-sirkulaerokonomi-prosjekt/>). An example of the publication on *Dagsavisen* is presented in Figure 3. The entire article can be accessed via the provided link.

NYHETER

Fredrikstad med i internasjonalt sirkulærøkonomi-prosjekt

Viken fylkeskommune og Fredrikstad kommune har til sammen fått 14 millioner kroner av EU til å jobbe med et internasjonalt sirkulærøkonomiprojekt

Daglig leder for Batteriretur AS kaller Fredrikstad sirkulærøkonomiens hovedstad. Nå skal kommunen inn i et stort samarbeidsprosjekt for å bli bedre på gjenbruk av ressurser. (Foto: Kenneth Stensrud)

Figure 3. Publication about TREASoURcE in Dagsavisen

8.1.3 Project website

Operational as of Month 3, the project website <https://treasource.eu/> has been created to serve as a central information point for the various stakeholders and media; it has been designed to be the main information repository for the project, its objectives, results and findings, and all activities related to its developments and progress. Since the website was published on August 16th, 2022 and as of September 30th, when this report is finalized, the TREASoURcE website has reached a total of 828 visits, which makes an average of 118 visits per week.

8.1.4 Social media

The project social media accounts were set up at the beginning of the project (by M1).

Since we began our activity on social media on June 23rd, 2022 and as of September 30th, when this report is finalized, TREASoURcE has gained 41 followers on Twitter and 107 on LinkedIn. The visibility the project has gained on Twitter is currently not fully reflected by the number of followers, since TREASoURcE Twitter has gained a total of 4702 profile visits during the first three months (June-August 2022).

Figure 4. TREASoURcE profile on Twitter

Figure 5. TREASoURcE profile on LinkedIn

8.1.5 Joint activities with CCRI

The representatives of CCRI and CCRI-CSO were invited to participate virtually to the project kick-off. The consortium members were given an introduction to the activities and role of CCRI and CCRI-CSO. Since the kick-off meeting was a physical meeting, the CCRI representatives didn't take part in work package updates or workshop activities that were part of the meeting. The key questions that had raised during the meeting were discussed at the end of the CCRI and CCRI-CSO introduction. Additionally, the project coordinator proposed on behalf of the whole consortium, that a CCRI representative would join the Advisory Board in order to ensure a close two-way exchange is established between the project and the CCRI.

Since the next consortium meeting is fixed as an online meeting, an invitation was made for the CCRI and CCRI-CSO representatives to participate also to work package updates to gain an even better insight to the project.

A dedicated Teams meeting was organized on August 30, 2022 between the CCRI and CCRI-CSO representatives and the TREASoURcE coordinator and Communication and Dissemination Manager to kick-off the cooperation. The project coordinator and Communication and Dissemination Manager will participate in the annual CCRI-CSO Coordination and Support Workshop held in Brussels on October 19, 2022. More activities will be carried out as planned in the Plan for joint activities with CCRI and relevant projects to create synergies presented in chapter 7.

A short introduction of CCRI is also included on TREASoURcE website, in the 'About' section, including a link to the Initiative's website.

Circular Cities and Regions Initiative

TREASoURcE is part of the European Union's Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI) that seeks to support the implementation of local and regional circular economy solutions. The CCRI is part of the new European Circular Economy Action Plan adopted in March 2020 and will also provide a local contribution to the implementation of the European Green Deal and the European bioeconomy strategy. It places cities and regions at the heart of the EU's green transition. TREASoURcE builds close collaboration and synergies with the CCRI and other circular economy projects and initiatives.

Find more information on [CCRI's website](#)

Figure 6. CCRI on TREASoURcE website

8.2 Upcoming activities (M5-M18)

Several opportunities for communication and dissemination activities have already been identified for the upcoming months, i.e. until the end of the first reporting period. The list is not exhaustive, further activities are likely to be added. A dedicated workshop was organised by WP8 (in M3) to map the WP-specific communication activities and needs for support. Some preliminary elements and insights were gained during the workshop, but further input is needed once the work package teams have had the time to organise themselves and do further planning of the activities. Another workshop to update the information and finetune the upcoming plans will be organised by M7 during the next (online) consortium meeting. A summary of planned activities for M5-M18 is presented in Table 6.

Table 4. Preliminary workplan for M5-M18

Timing	Type of activity	Description	Related WPs
M5-M7	Event	Klimapartnere meeting (Norway) – Presenting TREASoURcE at the meeting	WP2
	Event	Climate Viken Conference – Presenting TREASoURcE at the conference	WP2
	Publication	Blog post on the background and motivations behind TREASoURcE initiative	WP8 (WP9)
	Publication	First newsletter published	WP8, all
	Publication	Promotional materials finished and published on the website (general presentation, brochure)	WP8
	Publication	Social media campaign to present TREASoURcE partners ('people behind TREASoURcE')	WP8, all
	Event	CCRI-CSO Coordination and Support workshop participation	WP9, WP8
M8-M12	Publication	Executive summary and/or blog post on D1.1	WP1
	Publication	3 M.Sc. thesis completed, publications available	WP1
	Event	M.Sc. thesis presented e.g. at an open webinar	WP1
	Publication	Executive summary, website article and/or blog post on D1.4	WP1
	Publication	CE awareness Social media campaign incl. key messages from D1.1 & D1.4	WP1, WP8
	Publication	Podcast about CE for general public	WP2, WP8
	Publication	Series of short videos and texts of case presentations about CE companies (business opportunities, job creation)	WP2, WP8
	Publication	Website article/blog post and targeted social media campaign to inform about the demo sites once determined	WP4
	Publication	Executive summary and/or website article on workshop report including local CE conditions analysis	WP6
	Publication	Second newsletter published	WP8, all
M13-M18	Publication	Press releases in national languages (Finland, Norway) once battery demos are in place	WP4, WP8
	Publication	Third newsletter published	WP8, all

In addition to the activities described above, regular communication activities will be executed by WP8, such as updating the TREASoURcE website and social media channels (following the overall plan for Phase 1 as presented in the CDP), supporting other WPs in their activities, supporting participation to events and so on. The content creation will be coordinated with all consortium partners.

Annexes

The following annexes added to the final version of this document:

Annex 1: Brand guidelines

Annex 2: TREASoURcE social media guide for the consortium

Annex 3: PowerPoint template

TREASoURcE

Annex 1: Brand guidelines

TREASoURcE

Brand guidelines

06/2022

Visual appearance

Logo	1
Colours	2
Typography.....	3
Graphic elements	4–5
Images	6

Clear space and permitted use of the logo

Four-colour

Black (greyscale)

Negative (greyscale)

Negative (on diamond background)

Clear space

CMYK = 68, 0, 100, 0
RGB = 83, 182, 19
Pantone 368 C
#53b613

CMYK = 87,27, 100, 16
RGB = 7, 118, 3
Pantone 364 C
#077603

CMYK = 2, 27, 96, 0
RGB = 248, 191, 0
Pantone 7408 C
#f8bf00

CMYK = 0,59, 89, 0
RGB = 245, 128, 35
Pantone 158 C
#f58023

CMYK = 52, 70, 0, 0
RGB = 161, 93, 192
Pantone 7441 C
#a15dc0

CMYK = 67,92,9,1
RGB = 115, 51, 129
Pantone 7663 C
#733381

BLACK

CMYK = 77,56,48,46
RGB = 54,70,79
Pantone 432 C
#36464f

CMYK = 64,38,34,16
RGB = 95,124,138
Pantone 5415 C
#5f7c8a

CMYK = 20,10,7,0
RGB = 211,221,230
Pantone 642 C
#d3dde6

Arial

Black

**ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZÄÖ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyzåö
1234567890**

Regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZÄÖ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyzåö
1234567890

Italic

*ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZÄÖ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyzåö
1234567890*

Bold

**ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZÄÖ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyzåö
1234567890**

Graphic elements as a part of the visual appearance

Different background options have been designed for use with the TREASoURcE logo on various templates (PPT template, Word template). The background designs are fixed, and the graphic elements must not be altered to maintain a consistent visual appearance.

Lisää otsikko napsauttamalla

- Lisää teksti napsauttamalla

Funded by the European Union

5

Graphic elements as a part of the visual appearance

TREASoURcE's signature visual appearance includes the different versions of the diamond background that can be used together with the negative logo and white text according to the examples (PPT template, title slides) or black text (PPT template, content slides; Word template).

Project logos and text

All materials must always include the project logo and the EU logo with the funding statement in accordance with the layout shown in the example.

Images

Our images are fresh, clean and clear in colour. Strive to find images that have a calm and balanced colour scheme, layout and content.

TREASoURcE

Annex 2: TREASoURcE social media guide for the consortium

TREASoURcE

TREASoURcE Social media

Social media guide for the consortium

06/2022

Funded by
the European Union

TREASoURcE

TREASoURcE Profiles

Twitter, LinkedIn

TREASoURcE

Twitter

- TREASoURcE on Twitter: https://twitter.com/TREASoURcE_eu
- Handle: @TREASoURcE_eu
- Hashtag: #TREASoURcE

TREASoURcE

LinkedIn

- TREASoURcE on LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/treasure/>
- Handle: @TREASoURcE
- Hashtag: #TREASoURcE

Recommendations & tips

Handles and hashtags

Project handles

@TREASoURcE_eu (Twitter)

@TREASoURcE (LinkedIn)

Horizon Europe handles

@HorizonEU (Twitter)

@Horizon Europe (LinkedIn)

CCRI handles

@Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI) (LinkedIn)

Recommended hashtags

#TREASoURcE

#HorizonEU

#horizoneurope

#CCRIEurope

#euproject

#CCRIProject

#innovation

#research

#circulareconomy

#circularity

Other hashtags

#sustainability

#valuechain

#plastics

#batteries

#biobased

#circularplastics

#circularbatteries

#recycling

#cities

#regions

Tips

- Always use the TREASoURcE handle (@) or hashtag (#) when tweeting about the project through partner social media channels
- You can also tag @HorizonEU or @CCRI or use #HorizonEU, #horizoneurope or #CCRIEurope hashtags. Horizon Europe or CCRI may retweet or share project posts on their channels
- Like, retweet and share (with or without your comment) the posts through partner social media channels
 - Consider also the option of sharing with a comment in your native language for wider outreach!

TREASoURce Social media guide

WP8 Kaisa Simola

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TREASoURcE

List of changes

Date	Description of changes
19/07/22	LinkedIn Company page info added

TREASoURcE

Annex 3: PowerPoint template

TREASoURcE

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